

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

CONSTITUTIONAL VIDEO

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D6.4 – CONSTITUTIONAL VIDEO

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April, 2025 (M10) – WP6, T6.1

Co-funded by
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Technical References

Project Acronym	ENERGIZE
Project Title	SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

Deliverable No. & Title	D6.4 – Constitutional video
Type of deliverable	R (document, report) + DEC (videos)
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP6 – Sustainability, replication, exploitation plan
Lead beneficiary	3 – ESTRATS
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	8 – FEDARENE, 1 – IRIS
Due date of deliverable	30 April 2025
Actual submission date	30 April 2025

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Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
0.1	10/04/2025	1 st draft version of the deliverable	Olga BARRACHINA
1.0	30/4/2025	Final version of the deliverable	Segis VERDAGUER

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Executive Summary

ENERGIZE project is cofounded by the European Commission through the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program. ENERGIZE aims to demonstrate the potential of cooperative energy models in industrial zones across the EU. These initiatives face considerable challenges -especially in governance, legal frameworks and financial sustainability- which ENERGIZE aims to overcome. It will promote energy collaboration through active engagement, capacity building, and the creation of a dedicated digital hub to serve as a support tool. This approach will foster renewable energy projects, resource efficiency, and circularity within these communities.

This document describes the preparation and production of the constitutional video of ENERGIZE project.

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1 Introduction

The ENERGIZE project considers the development of different dissemination material, in views to increase the visibility of the project's outcomes and maximise the engagement of stakeholders and target groups within the project development.

Within this framework, a constitutional video explaining the project approach and expected impact has been produced. It will be used as key promotional material in the different social media channels of the project, as well as in presentations, conferences and public event.

Following the Grant Agreement, the ENERGIZE constitutional video has been created in English, and the expected delivery date of the deliverable is M10.

Several screenshots of the video are included within this document. The video itself will be available to be downloaded in the website of the project, as well as in the ENERGIZE Youtube channel during May 2025.

2 Screenplay of the video

Our ENERGIZE introductory video serves as a key communication tool to raise awareness about the benefits of energy cooperation among businesses within the same industrial area, and how these opportunities connect to the ENERGIZE project. The video is designed to engage industrial stakeholders and inspire them to explore and follow the project and adopt its outcomes.

The 1-minute and 25-second animated video uses a compelling visual narrative: it begins with grey and dark tones to represent a polluted, conventional industrial area, gradually transitioning to vibrant greens and bright colors to depict the transformation into a sustainable, renewable-powered industrial zone.

A voice-over guides viewers through this visual journey, following a clear and engaging structure that illustrates the project's vision, tools, and expected impact:

- A- Introduction and challenge
- B- The proposed solution
- C- ENERGIZE project

The voice-over narration is presented in the table below:

Table 2-1

Phase A Introduction and challenge	Industrial businesses face a major challenge: rising energy costs, supply uncertainties, dependence on fossil fuels, and increasingly strict regulations. This dependence leaves businesses vulnerable to price hikes and supply disruptions, hindering their growth and competitiveness.
Phase B The proposed solution	To stay competitive, industries must rethink their approach to energy. To make it happen, a new way of managing energy is emerging—one where companies collaborate rather than compete, working together to reduce costs and improve their competitiveness: The Industrial energy communities.
Phase C ENERGIZE project	ENERGIZE will help industrial parks create energy communities, unlocking new economic opportunities through innovative cooperation models and expert support. ENERGIZE transforms industrial zones into sustainable energy hubs.

3 Visual aspect

The following images, arranged in chronological order, illustrate the graphic design approach used throughout the different sections of the video.

Figure 3-1 – Video screenshot, example 1

Figure 3-2 – Video screenshot, example 2

Figure 3-3 – Video screenshot, example 3

Figure 3-4 – Video screenshot, example 4

Figure 3-5 – Video screenshot, example 5

Figure 3-6 – Video screenshot, example 6

Figure 3-7 – Video screenshot, example 7

Figure 3-8 – Video screenshot, example 8

4 Online repository

The video will be available through the project website (www.energizecommunity.eu) as well as through the ENERGIZE Youtube channel. The communication and dissemination actions planned for next months will also include the dissemination of the video through the different channels (LinkedIn and Instagram particularly).

Direct temporary link (for internal validation purposes, version without subtitles):

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1M7Si0scfe1pfPTFkupAysIAOYckX5vZE/view?usp=drive_link

More information: www.energizcommunity.eu

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